

ISSN: 0976-8031

Available Online at <http://www.recentscientific.com>

International Journal of Recent Scientific Research
Vol. 3, Issue, 7 pp. 137-144 October, 2011

**International Journal of
Recent Scientific
Research**

Research Article

STUDIES ON SEX EDUCATION AND SEX RELATIONSHIPS OF EDUCATION

Jayanthi C*

Department of Education, Annamalai University, Tamilnadu, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History:

Received 12th July, 2011
Received in revised form 29th August,
2011 Accepted 20th September, 2011
Published online 23th October, 2011

Key Words:

Society, Sex education, individual,
Student.

ABSTRACT

As social beings living in a society, we form opinions about others and others have opinions about us. Everybody wants to acceptance and recognition from and within society. We are also tried to behave according to the norms of the society so that we could adjust with others. But which is not an easy task as the personality of each individual is a unique organization. This organization has to make special efforts to adjust with others unique organizations, which we call as society. Actually adjustment is a wider term used in various spheres of life. For an example, if an individual is well-adjusted with his family environment, his family adjustment will be good. So before defining social adjustment is necessary for us to restrict the area of social adjustment. In other words we can say that social adjustment is the direction to the teachers, try to adjustment skill in our students. As a teachers should emphasize on the adjustment of the student in the school.

Copyright © Jayanthi C, 2016, this is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

Sex education, sometimes called sexuality education or sex and relationships education, is the process of acquiring information and training attitudes and beliefs about sex, sexual identity, relationships and intimacy. It is also about developing young people skills so that they make informed about their behaviour, and feel confident and competent about acting on these choices. It is widely accepted that young people have the right to sex education, partly because it is a mean by which they are helped to protect themselves against abuse, exploitation, unintended pregnancies sexually transmitted diseases and HIV/AIDS.

The science- only discourse, when coupled with exclusive renderings of sexual experiences, leads students to believe that certain sexual behaviors are wrong, and that those students who may have an interest in enacting them dually go against the laws of nature and are choosing to be unhealthy and unnatural. In reducing the risk Understanding Self-Identify, students are taught about sexualities through a science frame work. This is the only part the whole reducing the risk where students self-identity and uniqueness is discussed, yet this section is somehow the most science-based and sterilized. This is problematic because self- identities, especially when it comes to sexual orientation and gender identity are extremely personal feelings that shouldn't be qualified or categorized by outsiders looking into a person's experience.

Human sexuality is not limited to the life transmission or reproduction as it includes four important dimensions (i) Anatomy and biology with sex physiology , procreation and survival mankind (ii) Social dimension with cultural influence , social norms and rules and theirs political ,juridical and religious incidences (iii) Psychological dimension with gender issue , the personality construction and self-esteem and (iv) Affective and relational dimension with feelings (love , desire) , points of view and emotions .

Apart from the media, the peer group plays a major role with regard to adolescents, sexual behaviour (Sadock, 2005; Chambers, Walkey, Chambers, 2001, Ricers and Gabel, 1995). Many adolescents experiment with a new experience including sexual activity because of peer pressure. Peers have strong influence on adolescents desire to have sexual relations. Some wish to achieve the transition to adulthood at an earlier age than their peers (Rosenthal Smith and De visser, 1999). Others want to have experiences to share with their friends: some feel embarrassed if they do not have sexual experience or remain virgins (Sadock, 2005). However, not all adolescents think and behave the same way. Some pay attention or get involve in having sexual activity, but others do not. It varies by individuals personal values and beliefs and other associated factors.

They favour sex education for 12 years old and favour teaching them about a number of very explicit topics including AIDS and other sexually transmitted disease,

birth control, premarital sex abortion and homosexuality (Nokwe 1991). have explained that the knowledge about sex education depends on the attitudes of teaching who will be responsible in teaching situation and on the attitudes of parents who play vital part in the informal education of the learner. In his study he found that many people support that sex education must be offered as a separate course at schools. Supporting the view of informal education. (Gallagher and Gallagher,(1990) Steele, (1999) noted that infants and toddlers received sexuality education through when the parents talk to them, dress them, show affection and teach them the names of their body parts. They emphasize also that sex education begins at an early stage of a child (Steinberg 1996).

Recommended that sex education programmes, include clear information about how to obtain and use contraceptives. He further said that studies show that increasing adolescents' knowledge about sex education has a little impact-positive or negative on their sexual behavior. If sexuality education is to be successful. It must reflect, or at least accept, the cultures of the participants (Hyder and DeLamater, 1998). In supporting this view Khathide, (2001) said that it is the time for the pretence to come to an end and people have to talk about sex education in the languages they understand.

Parents rank second as actual source of sex education information Many authors view this as a problematic as peers providing less accurate information than teachers or health professional Hyder and De lamater, (1997).This lack of trust in teachers knowledge or discretion served to inhibit many young learners from approaching their teachers for information or advice about sex education (Moore and Rosenthal, 1993).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study intends to measure the attitude of sex education of higher secondary school students, in relation to their Adolescent Emotional Adjustment and Social adjustment. This chapter on methodology explains the sample chosen, for the study tools used, procedure of data collection, and the method of analysis of data.

The first step of the development of this scale was the collection of items for which at the first stage several books, journals, novels, newspapers were scanned to obtain a wide variety of statements pertaining to the sex education. For covering broadly the area of sex education, the statements covering all the area of sex education also were collected from the discussion of youths, adolescents and experts in the field of education and sex education. Considering all these views the investigator with the help of her guide prepared 106 items for the present tool.

The sex education attitude scale thus prepared was administered to a random sample of 100, XI standard students in Cuddalore Educational District. The pilot study was mainly conducted to eliminate any ambiguity and find out if students experience any difficulty in

responding to the sex education attitude scale. It was emphasized to answer all the items; no time-limit was fixed. However, it took approximately 45 minutes to complete. In the pilot study sex education attitude scale, there were 106 items.

The scoring procedure of the present scale is very simple. Each statement has five responses wise SA, A, UD, D and SD. The subject was asked to read each statement carefully and express their views freely by putting a tick mark against any one of the five options. For positive statements 5, 4,3,2,1 marks were given and for negative statements 1, 2,3,4,5 marks were given. The summated scores of the sex education attitude scale were thus found out for each statement and for all the 100 individuals.

Item-Analysis and Item selection

After the pilot study the investigator decided to seek whether the observed responses are really significant or merely chance fluctuations. Therefore null hypothesis were set for each items. So the chi-square values for all the statements are calculated in order to build up final scale.

The chi-square values of all the 106 statements for a df of 4 are given in table no. 10. The chi-square value for a df of 4 at 0.01 level is 13.277. From the table it is evident that the chi-square values of the items which are greater than 13.277 were significant at 0.01level. Therefore the null hypotheses in respect of this statement were rejected at 0.01 level. The chi-square values of the items which are less than 13.277 were non-significant at 0.01 level. Therefore the null hypothesis in respect of these statements were accepted at 0.01 level. From that it was calculated that the deviations of the observed responses from the expected distribution were really significant for 40 statements out of 106 statements and not a matter of chance. Therefore 40 statements in the scale were retained for final study. Out of the 40 statements 10 statements each were related general factor, social factor, individual mental factor and individual physical factor respectively. A few verbal changes wherever found necessary, as expert opinion were carried out in the final tool.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data of the present study involved 600 higher secondary students, belonging to Cuddalore educational district. In order to find out the objectives of the present study, the following statistical methods have been employed by the investigator find out the results of the study. The data collected from 600 higher secondary students in Cuddalore educational district who were taken as sample. The descriptive analysis, includes means and standard deviations to assess the levels of the existence of the variables namely attitude of sex education, adolescent emotional adjustment, and social adjustment. The differential analysis involves 't'-test. The researcher has

used the 't'-test to find out the significance of the mean difference between two groups,

Correlation analysis as used to find out the relationship between the dependent variable and other independent variables. The correlation co-efficient is valuable in the field of education as a measure of relationship between test scores. Through there are several methods of calculating correlation co-efficient. Mean and

standard deviation of attitude towards introduction of sex education scores- Dimension I General factor It may be recalled that the attitude towards the introduction of sex education in relation to certain selected sub-samples were analysed Dimension wise. The analysis of dimension I general factors is calculated and the results are discussed in table.

Dimension I General factor

Table1. Mean and standard deviation of attitude towards introduction of sex education scores- Dimension I General factor

S.No	Categories	N	M Maxi.50	SD	Level	
Entire - sample attitude towards introduction of sex Education		600	36.38	6.13	HF	
1.	Gender	Male	274	36.35	5.52	HF
		Female	326	36.40	6.60	HF
2.	Religion	Hindu	455	36.05	6.41	HF
		Christian	60	36.32	5.42	HF
		Muslim	85	38.15	4.61	HF
3	Type of management	Government	363	36.83	6.30	HF
		Aided	217	35.94	5.48	HF
		Private	20	33.05	8.26	HF
4	Locality	Urban	142	36.54	5.79	HF
		Rural	458	36.90	6.24	HF
5	Type of school	Co education	476	36.11	6.43	HF
		Boys	101	37.27	4.46	HF
		Girls	23	38.09	5.70	HF
6	Parental education	Illiterate	183	35.70	7.08	HF
		School level	367	36.59	5.64	HF
		Graduate	40	37.13	5.77	HF
		Professional	10	38.20	5.71	HF
7	Family type	Joint	183	37.00	5.63	HF
		Nuclear	417	36.11	6.32	HF

From the table no. 4.3, it may be inferred that the mean of Dimension - I (General factor) of attitude towards introduction of sex education of higher secondary students is 36.38. This indicates that there is highly favourable attitude towards introduction of sex education of the general factors. Although all the sub-samples are having favourable attitude towards introduction of sex education of general factor there are slight differences among the variables. Female students, students of muslim religion, government school students, rural students, girls school students, students of professional parents and students of

joint family are having more favourable attitude towards introduction of the sex education general factor than their respective counterparts.

The standard deviation scores of all the factors show greater consistency among themselves. Mean and standard deviation of attitude towards introduction of sex education scores- Dimension II Social factor It may be recalled that the attitude towards the introduction of sex education in relation to certain selected sub-samples were analyzed Dimension wise the analyses of dimension II Social factors is calculated and the results are discussed.

Dimension - II Social factor

Table .2. Mean and standard deviation of attitude towards introduction of sex education scores- Dimension II - Social factor

S.No	Categories	N	M Maxi.50	SD	Level	
	Entire - sample attitude towards introduction of sex education	600	40.47	6.76	HF	
1.	Gender	Male	274	39.98	6.93	HF
		Female	326	40.87	6.59	HF
2.	Religion	Hindu	45.5	39.91	7.01	HF
		Christian	60	41.30	4.57	HF
		Muslim	85	42.86	6.10	HF
3	Type of management	Government	363	40.06	6.96	HF
		Aided	217	41.49	5.96	HF
		Private	20	36.70	9.05	HF
4	Locality	Urban	142	41.90	7.42	HF
		Rural	458	40.02	6.48	HF
5	Type of school	Co education	476	40.42	6.81	HF
		Boys	101	40.79	6.96	HF
		Girls	23	39.87	4.61	HF
6	Parental education	Illiterate	183	40.52	6.81	HF
		School level	367	40.65	6.84	HF
		Graduate	40	39.10	5.30	HF
		Professional	10	37.90	7.46	HF
7	Family type	Joint	183	40.14	6.69	HF
		Nuclear	417	40.61	6.79	HF

HF- Highly Favourable

From the table no. 4.4, it may be inferred that the mean of Dimension - II (social factor) of attitude towards introduction of sex education of higher secondary students is $M = 40.47$ which is highly favourable. This indicates that there is highly favourable attitude towards the social factor among higher secondary students. Although all the sub-samples are having favourable attitude towards introduction of sex education of general factor there are slight differences among the variables. Female students, students of muslim religion, government school students, rural students, girls school students, students of professional parents and students of joint family are

having more favourable attitude towards introduction of the sex education general factor than their respective counterparts. The standard deviation scores of all the factors show greater consistency among themselves. Mean and standard deviation of attitude towards introduction of sex education scores- Dimension III individual physical factor

It may be recalled that the attitude towards the introduction of sex education in relation to certain selected sub-samples were analysed Dimension wise the analyses of dimension III individual physical factors is calculated and the results are discussed in table.

Dimension - III Individual physical factor

Table .3. Mean and standard deviation of attitude towards introduction of sex education scores Dimension III- individual physical factor

S.No	Categories	N	M Maxi.50	SD	Level	
Entire – sample		600	36.38	5.28	HF	
1.	Gender	Male	274	36.45	5.03	HF
		Female	326	36.87	5.49	HF
2.	Religion	Hindu	455	36.74	5.61	HF
		Christian	60	36.97	4.51	HF
		Muslim	85	36.14	3.82	HF
3	Type of management	Government	363	36.79	5.55	HF
		Aided	217	36.65	4.57	HF
		Private	20	34.85	7.26	HF
4	Locality	Urban	142	36.06	4.56	HF

		Rural	458	36.87	5.48	HF
5	Type of school	Co education	476	36.94	5.50	HF
		Boys	101	35.65	3.87	HF
		Girls	23	35.78	5.59	HF
6	Parental education	Illiterate	183	37.03	5.86	HF
		School level	367	36.64	5.02	HF
		Graduate	40	35.65	4.45	HF
		Professional	10	35.70	6.62	HF
7	Family type	Joint	183	36.28	5.40	HF
		Nuclear	417	36.85	5.22	HF

HF- Highly Favorable

Although all the sub-samples are having favourable attitude towards introduction of sex education of general factor there are slight differences among the variables. Female students, students of muslim religion, government school students, rural students, girls school students, students of professional parents and students of joint family are having more favourable attitude towards introduction of the sex education general factor than their respective counterparts. The standard deviation scores of all the factors show greater consistency among themselves.

Conclusion

After the detailed and through analysis the results were found out. Based on that finding and discussion are made in the succeeding chapters.

Student's gender and locality played a dominant role in their knowledge about sex education significantly boys and urban locality students are more favorable attitude than their counterparts. Further parental education and occupation also played significant role. Generally parents are not freely discussing with their wards. This is also noticed from the findings. So special counseling should be given to parents regarding sex education and to disseminate it to students. In the case of locality and gender special programmes should be organized for girl children and children from rural background.

Reference

1. Sadock, B.J., (2005). Kaplan & Sadock's comprehensive textbook of psychiatry (8th ed.).

- Philadelphia, PA: Lippincott, Williams, & Wilkins.
2. Chambers, R.G. and J. Quiggin (2001), 'Production externalities and multitask principal agent problems', Working Paper, Australian National University. Canberra.
 3. Gabel, Matthew, and Harvey Palmer. 1995. "Understanding Variation in Public Support for European Integration." *European Journal of Political Research* 27:3-19.
 4. Nokwe, J. K. (1991). The attitudes of teachers and parents towards offering sex education as a separate course in Senior Secondary Schools. Unpublished B.Ed. dissertation, Umtata: University of Transkei.
 5. DeLamater, John, Hyde, Janet Shibley, 1998. Essentialism vs. social constructionism in the study of human sexuality. *J. Sex. Res.* 35, 10–18.
 6. KHATHIDE, Agrippa. 2001. What A Giant of Faith: The story of Richard Ngidi's Ministry of Miracles. Semper Nova.
 7. Moore, S., & Rosenthal, D. (1993). *Sexuality in adolescence*. New York: Routledge
 8. Bajwa, R., T. Anjum, S. Shafique and S. Shafique. 2006. Evaluation of antifungal activity of *Cicer arietinum* L. *Pak. J. Bot.*, 38(1): 175 - 184.
 9. P. P. Talukdar, J. Reisinger, M. Pasca, D. Ravichandran, R. Bhagat, and F. Pereira. 2008. WeaklySupervised Acquisition of Labeled Class Instances using Graph Random Walks. In *Proceedings of the 2008 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, pages 581–589.
 10. Singh R, et al. (2006) Struct2net: integrating structure into protein-protein interaction prediction. *Pac Symp Biocomput* 403-14.
 11. Singh J, et al. (2005) Transcriptional response of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* to desiccation and rehydration. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 71(12):8752-63
 12. Mehta, S.Q., Hiesinger, P.R., Beronja, S., Zhai, R.G., Schulze, K.L., Verstreken, P., Cao, Y., Zhou, Y., Tepass, U., Crair, M.C., Bellen, H.J. (2005). Mutations in *Drosophila* sec15 reveal a function in neuronal targeting for a subset of exocyst components. *Neuron* 46(2): [219--232](#).